

THE ACTION OF INORGANIC COLLOIDS ON ELECTRODEPOSITION OF NICKEL.

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The electrodeposition of nickel sulphate bath on copper plates in the presence of Prussian blue, silver, ferric oxide and arsenious sulphide sols has been studied. A dull and very rough deposit is obtained in the presence of arsenious sulphide, while the presence of other sols yields a comparatively lustrous and smooth deposit. The nature and concentration of the sol seem to affect the nature and amount of deposit.

When a strip of zinc is dipped in a solution of lead acetate, a bright crystalline 'tree' is obtained. If glue has been added to the bath solution, an amorphous looking deposit results. A tin tree exhibits a similar phenomenon.

Mueller Bahntje (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1906, 12, 317) found that copper deposited in the presence of colloids weighed 0.2% more than the metal deposited without the colloid. They found that gelatine had the most powerful effect, egg-albumin considerably less and gum and starch had no action. Investigators in the realm of electrodeposition of nickel have mainly occupied themselves in determining the influence of organic colloids on the nature of deposit. They have been using the above mentioned colloids and in certain cases, essential oils (*cf.* Mathers and Cockrum, *Met. Chem. Eng.*, 1914, 12, 714; Mathers and Leible, *Chem. Abst.*, 1917, 11, 1792). The investigation of the action of inorganic colloids forms the subject of the present paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The bath used was obtained by mixing equal volumes of nickel sulphate solution (78.56 g. per litre) and boric acid and potassium chloride (30 g. and 19 g. per litre respectively). Nickel sulphate was obtained by recrystallisation of the B.D.H. sample. Its concentration was determined by precipitation as barium sulphate in an aliquot portion. The other reagents were analytically pure.

Copper plates (6" × 1") were taken and rubbed till free from the oxide layer. They were rinsed with water and alcohol and dried before use.

The cathode was further subjected to the following cleansing treatment successively :

(a) It was dipped to form the cathode in a 5% solution of sodium hydroxide and sodium carbonate, and then rinsed with water.

(b) It was dipped in a 10% solution of KCN which was followed by a water rinse.

(c) It was electrically cleaned as in (a) and finally it was dipped in 10% sulphuric acid and washed with water and alcohol.

The loss in weight sustained by the cathode, as determined in five experiments, was approximately 0.004-0.005% of the weight of the plate. Current was adjusted till a uniform deposit of copper and nickel was obtained. Current of 0.2 ampere if passed for about 30 minutes gave a suitable deposit. An increase in the current strength resulted in the separation of nickel in a spongy form.

Three different colloids were tried. The addition of colloids produces no effect on the calculated theoretical amount of nickel deposited. The results are given below.

Prussian Blue Hydrosol.

M/28-Potassium ferrocyanide (20 c.c.) was taken and 60 c. c. of water were added to it. Glycerine (5 drops) was then mixed with it to stabilise the colloid. Ferric chloride (20 c. c., *M/27*-approximately) was then added drop by drop followed by continuous shaking. A deep blue coloration resulted.

Quantitatively there is no appreciable effect on the amount of metal deposited, but the nature of deposit undergoes a change as seen from the plates.

Plate B shows the nature of the surface when no colloid has been added, while Plate A exhibits the initial character of the cathode. It will be seen that the abrasion marks are straight and do not show any tendency to cross-grain. In the nickel-plated surface the pitch of the lines is definitely altered. The deposit is not very hard or coherent.

Plate C-side opposite the anode. Addition of 5 c. c. of the hydrosol resulted in the decrease in the number of abrasion marks and the size of the grain of the depositing nickel was much reduced. The plate after deposit took on a lustre which was absent in Plate B, and the deposit was hard.

With 10 c. c. of the hydrosol, the plate D has a marked resemblance to Plates A and B showing that the thickness of the deposit is just enough to cover the copper cathode, while it is insufficient to overlap the inherent defects of the plate.

With 15 c. c. of the hydrosol Plate E shows the effect of such an addition. A study of this leads one to conclude that the strength of the colloid has exceeded the upper limit of its optimum concentration. A close examination reveals that nickel has been loosely deposited. It appears that the large amount of the colloid renders considerable reduction in the size of the grain.

Silver Hydrosol.

The hydrosol was obtained by mixing 5 c.c. of 1 % silver nitrate solution with water so as to make 100 c.c. It was then warmed and to this 3 c.c. of 1% sodium carbonate solution were added. Freshly prepared tannin (1%, 1 to 3 c.c.) was dropped in gradually until a deep yellowish brown colouration developed. The solution became transparent on dilution.

Plate G shows the nature of the deposit when 5 c.c. of the above sol are added. It is noticed that the solution is more potent than the previous one. A definite reduction in grain size takes place all over the surface, and the cross-graining is also uniform. Plate H shows the effect of 15 c.c. of the sol. Under the magnification used, the surface appears to be almost without the abrasion marks. Such a plate can take a high polish subsequently with a marked ease. Besides, the deposit is hard and coherent.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol.

The sol was prepared in the usual manner by passing hydrogen sulphide through a saturated and filtered solution of arsenious oxide. Before boiling off the gas it was seen that all the arsenic had been precipitated as the sulphide. Hydrogen sulphide was removed by boiling and bubbling hydrogen gas through the colloidal solution.

The solution was mechanically stirred throughout the experiment otherwise the colloid settled down and altered the concentration of the sol, in the different parts of the bath.

It appears that the colloid hinders the deposition of the metal. There is a wide discrepancy between the theoretical and the observed values. Moreover, it was seen that the metal was deposited as a loose, black spongy mass and this was easily removed with water. Plate J shows the condition of such a plate when 5 c. c. of the colloid were added. Grain-size reduction did take place but the deposit was neither hard nor coherent. Plate K shows the nature of the surface at the bottom of the plate. As the concentration of the colloid was greater in the

lower regions, small crystals of nickel could be perceptible. Even the naked eye can make out the roughness of the deposit which is dark and lacks lustre. In some places the copper is visible. This is shown in curved lines in Plate L.

D I S C U S S I O N .

Grube and Ruess (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1921, 27, 45) showed that irrespective of the charge on the colloid, the nickel ions form a complex with the colloid, which travels towards the cathode due to cataphoresis. This complex is decomposed on coming into contact with the plate and the metal is deposited. The nature of deposit depends on the nature of the complex. This is corroborated by the fact that some arsenious sulphide is found embedded in the cathode. This may also lead us to favour the adhesion theory which assumes the formation of a colloidal wall, of about molecular thickness round the cathode. Nickel ions have to penetrate this wall before they can get deposited. Thus it may be likened to percolation. The time taken for the process may be considerable and it is plausible to presume that some of the depositing Ni ions are embedded in the wall and have had no time to get deposited, when the current is switched off. The deficiency in the deposit is thus explained by the nature of the wall. As_2S_3 has a negative effect because it has a tendency to flocculate and agglomerate. This does not give a uniformly thick wall. Prussian blue and silver hydrosols impart a lustre to the plate, since in these cases there is no flocculation and all the crystals are in one plane and thus maximum brilliance due to reflection is obtained.

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Plate A.

Plate G.

Plate B.

Plate H.

Plate C.

Plate J.

Plate D.

Plate K.

Plate E.

Plate L.

